

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

TRANSPARENT PROCESSES FOR SMART WORK IN THE MOUNTAIN REALITY

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 8

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036).

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1. Introduction

This deliverable concerns the possible application of technologies and tools, that are mainly adopted by big companies, in smaller companies where tasks are often performed by executing informal, undocumented, or semi-documented processes.

We report about the demonstrative application of existing technologies to a real-world case, provided by a SME. The activity aimed at sensitizing the company about the possibilities allowed by the new technologies, in particular about the remote regulation and the control of complex tasks, and the possibility of performing what-if analyses on alternative organizations of the work or possible variations of the requests flow. The resulting demonstrator consists both of a specification of a likely but not really used business process, that relies on the standard notation BPMN, and of the extraction, from a dataset made of anonymized logs, of the actual processes that are carried out by the workers, a lore which often remains under the surface and that cannot be shared easily with new workers and that, due to its being beyond the horizon of the management, does not typically allow analysis and improvement. We also provide demonstrations of how different view over the same activities can be obtained by selecting and tuning the parameters of interest.

Greater awareness of the importance of such things as “processes”, indeed, creates the conditions for the adoption of practices and tools that allow not only the manager but also all the involved role players to actually “see” the progression of activities within the company, independently from where, geographically, the workers stand. This, in turn, can support trust in workers/management and an organization of work that is goal-driven. Monitoring, however, is not the only possible tool whose use is enabled. Tools for the analysis of log traces and process models allows the identification of stress conditions and weaknesses of the current (as well as of possible) ways in which activities are organized. Thus, they help the management in taking decisions about the possible reorganization of internal activities as well as about the acquisition/release of resources.

The activity was made possible thanks to the collaboration with an ICT company (for privacy reasons the name is not reported). The provided case is interesting for the following reasons. First, it concerns a target application that is distributed by nature; hence, it involves workers who are geographically distributed and do not necessarily know each other (a characteristic that is typical also of the remote working case). Second, despite being a medium-sized company whose core business is in the computer science area, and despite using a software tool for interacting with clients (a ticketing system), no formal description of the processes to be applied was used in practice by the workers involved in solving the received requests. Attempts had been made to design some processes, but they were never adopted by the workers on the field. This was mainly due to two reasons: 1) the ticket management software being somewhat liberal, not regimenting (inter)action; 2) a certain desire of the workers to be free to act as they deemed the most suitable way, without the burden of recording all the steps and decisions (in some cases already registered in other systems imposed by the end customer), for future analysis. The software infrastructure produced a lot of data but the most important information was hidden in emails and note fields.

The deliverable is organized into two main parts:

- The next section presents the process model that the company defined was not enforced by

the tool in practice. Process management techniques are discussed, showing the benefits that the company may get from the analysis that can be performed with them. These techniques have been presented and discussed with the company.

- The subsequent section presents an analysis of real data supplied by the company. The data capture activity logs, encoding the actual steps executed to handle actual tickets. Such executions show a pretty wide variety, helped by the adopted ticketing system. To perform this analysis process mining techniques have been introduced to the company. Since the company had to provide real data, an anonymization step on their side was necessary before the analysis could take place. An additional difficulty was that not all the interesting information could be shared at once from the start for two reasons: 1) the data had to be retrieved at different places in the system since it was stored in a database in a shape that did not suit the analysis tools; 2) more importantly, what is interesting and relevant also depends on the analysis that has been carried out so far, and on what the company deems to be relevant for itself as the work goes on. As a consequence, this second type of analysis is ongoing and the results contained in this report are partial. Regular meetings are being carried on with the company to complete the analysis.

1.1. Process Management Techniques for Transparency

We end this introduction by briefly sketching the main concepts of process management. One of the pillars on which companies and, more in general, organizations, rely are processes. A process defines what an entity does to achieve a goal, or to deliver a service (or a product) to a customer [1]. Business Process Management (BPM) aims at defining methodologies, tools, and techniques for process analysis so that they can be potentially improved.

The Business Process Management methodology consists of several steps organized into the BPM lifecycle (see Figure 1). The first step consists of the Process Design, whose result is a Process Model, i.e. a description of the process as expected to be executed. By Process Model we mean an abstract and structured representation, usually having a graphical format, of the steps performed in a process, under which conditions they are performed, and how these steps, called activities or tasks, are temporally related to one another (e.g., in sequences, alternative or parallel paths).

Process modeling is the first step in performing process analysis because it provides the means to define the object that will be analyzed. Starting from a process model, two main directions for process analysis are possible: 1) simulate the execution of the process to determine bottlenecks, need for resources or their waste, and so on; 2) perform conformance checking, which aims at comparing how the process is executed in reality (by analyzing execution logs) with how the process is expected to be performed in theory (as described in the process model).

Both types of analysis have been presented to the company and applied to some case studies and are presented in this deliverable.

M. Weske: Business Process Management,
© Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2007

Figure 1. BPM Lifecycle

2. Process Transparency through Process Modeling: the case study

The first step for process analysis is to gather information about the process: what the goal of the process is, when and how a process instance is supposed to start, what are the activities to be performed, in which orders and how do they synchronize, which are the involved organizational roles, and so on.

QUICK FACTS

sector: ICT

locations: 3

overall personnel: 140 units

services: design and implementation of solutions for Enterprise Networking, Cyber Security, Internet of Things, Data Center & Cloud e Digital Workplace; proactive management of the infrastructure, of cyber-security, of application performance; training for ICT professionals.

Box 1: brief description of the company.

The company (see Box 1 for an overview) was interested in analyzing the processes related to an application that is used for ticket management. Tickets can be generated either as a consequence of an explicit customer request or automatically by some software system.

This desire matched the purposes of NODES because ticket management is performed remotely with respect to the client, and the specialists who will, altogether, handle the request may also work remotely from one another and from the management. This is typical and communal to all remote working scenarios. The company also had difficulties in clearly understanding the potential of process management, this is why starting from a process that had already been designed by them by using non-specialized tools was a good start. We could show how proper means enable the automatic identification of weaknesses, as well as the possibilities offered by simulation.

Getting into the details, the company identifies three ticket types and, consequently, three different processes:

- *Incident Management*: it occurs when the customer signals some malfunctioning or problem to be solved;
- *Event Management*: it occurs for alarms automatically generated by the system; and
- *Technical Assistance and Request Fulfillment*: these occur when the customer requests some change in the infrastructure maintained by the company.

The analyses concerned the third category. The types of questions we aim to answer are: How is the Request Fulfillment process expected to be performed? What are the critical parts of the process, considering the workforce available in the company (e.g., bottlenecks)? How do changes in the process or the workforce affect the performance?

2.1. The Request Fulfillment Process

The first activity consisted in the analysis of a process description that was provided as a PDF document by the company. The model was developed using an invented notation, inspired by computer science workflows; it consists both of graphical and textual representations of the expected process executions.

The representation of the process, as supplied by the company, can be seen in Figure 2. Let us explain it. According to the textual description of the process, the company operates in a remote service delivery mode (performed from the company's headquarters). Upon receiving a Service Request from a customer, which can come via email, phone, or be submitted through the self-service portal, the company's technicians use dedicated connectivity (such as VPN) to connect to the Client's resources or Desktop Conferencing tools to provide the service. This service may consist of immediate execution of the request or deferred scheduling of the required intervention.

A support intervention is identified by the Assistance Request Number automatically assigned by the “ManageEngine Service Desk Plus MSP” system and by the information entered into the application, which links it to: the requester or contact person; the client's site and the associated client (account); or the support contract.

The support request is routed to the appropriate support coordinator technician. The ticketing system, indeed, allows for direct assignment of the CASE/Ticket (will be used as synonymous) or placing it in a queue to be picked up by one of the specialist technicians associated with the queue.

In both cases, the involved individuals, their respective managers, and the supervisors of the Technical Services Organizational Unit receive an email notification of the tasks assigned to them. When the support request (CASE) has been taken in charge by a technician, its state is changed to “In Progress/Troubleshooting”.

The technician delves into the analysis of the request, possibly getting in touch with the Client's contact person again and recording in the CASE the relevant details about the request. The technician asks for clarification until all of the client's needs are understood. During this analysis, the following actions may be carried out and should be documented using the logging functionalities of the CASE provided by the System:

- Specialist consultations (a request for further analysis from a Professional Service specialist or the manufacturer's support service);
- Research on specialized websites.

If the resolution of the CASE needs to be paused while waiting for information from the Client, this should be indicated by placing the CASE in an appropriate state.

The ticket management phase ends when the activities required to fulfill the request have been identified (e.g., reconfiguration, software patch installation, etc.). If the technician can execute the requested modification directly from remote, he will describe the solutions applied directly in the CASE and proceed to close the CASE in the system.

The subsequent phase consists of checking with the client that the problem has been solved. If this is the case, the CASE transits to the “closed” state.

Figure 2. Block Diagram Representing Service Request Management

2.2. Process Model

The process description supplied by the company is quite detailed and provides a graphical representation of the foreseen main steps. Interestingly, each activity represented in Figure 2 is assigned to a specific role of the company. Moreover, thanks to the graphical language, it is possible to easily grasp the main steps of the process from the diagram.

However, due to the language that was chosen for the representation, the diagram lacks important details, that are described in the document in textual form. More precisely, the diagram does not show alternative paths in the execution of the process but only captures the most frequent or most likely execution of the process. This may have several consequences:

- 1) when a process of this kind has to be implemented in the company's systems, one has to consider several sources of information, risking to overlook some aspects;
- 2) when changes need to be applied to the process one has to identify all parts that need to be adapted;
- 3) the graphical representation lacks alternative paths and conditions ruling the different paths;
- 4) it is not possible to use automatic tools to perform analysis (such as simulation) because the format of the process representation is not recognized. Specifically, no simulation tool on the market supports the graphical language that has been used by the company (the flow diagram was drawn with Igrafx or Microsoft Visio), and, more importantly, the model is incomplete or rather abstract.

2.3. Model redesign

As a first step in our analysis, we provide a BPMN-based representation of the process model, enriched with the details contained in the text. BPMN stands for “Business Process Modeling and Notation” and is the de-facto standard for process representation [1,2]. For the sake of presentation, in this deliverable, we report the compact version of the process model where complex activities are detailed in separate diagrams. Although being equivalent to the expanded version (where complex activities are represented in their expanded form in the diagram), the compact version is more suitable to be reported in a document. For the sake of completeness, we presented both formats to the company.

Figure 3 reports the BPMN process model. As the main differences to the version supplied by the company, in this version, we explicitly represent the interaction with the client and we report the decision points (graphically represented with a diamond) labelled with a question and with possible answers as labels of the outgoing branches. In summary, once a request is received from a customer, the technician identifies the client. This is a complex activity consisting of 1) identifying a reference person and 2) identifying the object of the request. There are no (temporal) dependencies between these two activities. This subprocess is reported in Figure 4. After this step, a CASE is assigned to the request (process instance) and the acquired information is associated with it. Once this is done, the contract validity is checked, and then the request is classified in terms of priority and type (Incident, or Service Request). Also, this one is a complex activity that is detailed in Figure 5.

Figure 3. BPMN representation of the Request Fulfillment Process

Figure 4. Client Identification Subprocess

Figure 5 details this process, showing that both the type of request and its priority need to be identified. The parallel gateway (depicted with a + symbol placed in a diamond shape) specifies that there is no temporal relation between these two activities, which can thus be performed in any order. The parallel gateway used as conjunction of the two branches specifies that only once both branches are concluded, the process can progress further.

Figure 5. Request Classification Subprocess

According to the process in Figure 4, after the request has been classified, the process continues with the identification of a suitable technician or a queue where to place the request. The state of the request is then changed to Troubleshooting and, if details are needed the request is investigated further with a number of request exchanges with the customer.

The request for details is a complex activity. We describe it in Figure 6. This subprocess captures that two levels of investigation of the request can be performed in parallel. On the one hand (top branches), if clarifications are needed from the customer, then these are requested to the customer and logged. This loop continues until no more clarifications are needed. On the other hand (bottom branches), if information on the resolution of the problem is needed, then both a specialist or the web can be inquired about it. Also, in this case, clarifications are then logged. This loop continues until no more clarifications on the resolution of the problem are needed.

Figure 6. Request in-depth analysis

Once this activity is completed, the technician checks whether the resolution activity can be performed remotely or not. In case it can, then it is performed, the state of the CASE is should be set to Solution Proposed and then the client is notified and the solution is checked. If the client is satisfied, the state of the CASE is set to solved and then the changes are logged.

2.4. Analysis of the model with the company

The presented BPMN process model was discussed with the company. We report the main considerations that emerged.

Level of Detail. The analysis clearly highlights how different activities are specified at very different levels of detail. We identified three cases:

1. Some activities are extremely detailed, that is, they amount to tasks that consist of a single step (atomic activities, e.g., changing the CASE state).
2. Others are, instead, complex activities, each made of many steps. In other words, these amount to subprocesses.
3. There is, then, a third class, so to say, of activities, whose specification is quite vague. Examples are “Perform Activity” (Eeguire Attività), “Assign request to Technician or to a queue” (Assegna tecnico o coda), and so on. Clearly such activities encompass many steps that are not specified. They allow some discretionality that remains under the responsibility of the involved workers. The process remains opaque.

A possible step for improving the process would be to make activities more homogenous and increase the level of detail by providing the specification of the subprocesses that are identified by those complex activities that remain underspecified in the current version.

Missing Activities. Besides being at different levels of detail, there are also missing activities in the process representation. For instance, suppose a request is first assigned to a Level 1 technician, that is a technician in charge of performing standard checks and identifying possible solutions to the problem. If none of the solutions works, the technician can pass the request to a Level 2 technician, who has more specific competencies. However, the possibility of passing a request from one technician to another is not captured in the model.

Missing alternatives. Decision points are represented by a diamond labeled with an X symbol. Considering the decision points in the model, one can see that not all possible executions are captured by the model. For example, the first decision point in the diagram aims at checking if the problem can be solved remotely or not. In case it cannot be solved remotely, the process does not clearly specify what steps need to be undertaken to solve it. Here we have a design incompleteness that should be solved. One of the properties that the design of a process model should respect is the objective of the process. If its goal is to solve a problem signaled with a request from a customer, then, all alternative paths that allow achieving the goal must be represented. In other words, the process model must be complete. Similarly, let us consider another example of incompleteness: the other decision points check whether the customer is happy with the solution of the CASE/Ticket. The process model does not represent what must be done if the customer believes the proposed solution is not good and the problem is not solved.

2.5. Model simulations

Besides the analysis performed in collaboration with the company's domain experts, we performed a complementary analysis by simulating the process execution. This technique can be proficiently implemented with the support of BPM tools. In this case, we used SAP Signavio¹ with the academic license. (other tools exist, such as Apromore [3], Pm4Py [4], or ProM [5]).

Process simulation allows one to define parameters such as the frequency by which new process instances are generated, the time required by each activity to be completed, the number of working resources that are available, and so on. By way of the simulation, it is possible to identify the time required by instances to complete, the cost of handling the requests, and the points in the process in which bottlenecks occur.

Usually, when performing a simulation, more than one scenario is defined. The difference between such scenarios lies in the values assigned to the parameters (number of resources, durations, costs, and such like). However, this information is sensible for the company; for this reason, it was not possible to simulate the process by using real data. To overcome the problem, we created two likely scenarios with the aim of showing the company the potential of this technique. For both scenarios, we defined very limited resources working for the company. Specifically, we considered one worker for each competence type (w.r.t. to Figure 3, one person with role SDT-TEC-S&S, one with role TEC-CT, and one TEC) working from Monday to Sunday from 8am to 5pm.

Scenario 1

In the first scenario, we specified very few parameters in order to have more control over the effects of the simulation: when changing only one of them it is easier to interpret the obtained results. In this scenario, instances were generated from Monday through Friday and were set to be 58 in total in a week. We specified a duration for two activities only, namely, the opening of a case (24 minutes, which is a reasonable guess) and the assignment of the ticket to a technician or to a queue. All activities whose duration is not specified were considered as instantaneous.

In correspondence with the discussed decision point, we set instances to be solvable remotely and not with equal probability. We simulated the evolution along a period of 30 (virtual) days. Not surprisingly, the process performances are very bad. Indeed, given the very little availability of resources, out of 1276 generated instances, only 437 reached the end of the process. Although

¹ <https://academic.signavio.com/p/login>

activities take, in general, little time to be performed (according to this simulation) each person playing a role must perform many, and we supposed only one resource per role to be available. Many tickets remain unprocessed.

Scenario 2

The second scenario contains richer information, in particular, it specifies a duration for each of the activities in the process. We used durations that were considered as reasonable by the experts from the company. So, for instance, we set higher durations for activities like "request in-depth analysis", which is set to take 5 hours.

Figure 7. Process simulation with Academic SAP Signavio Licence.

From the graphical representation of the simulation, shown in Figure 7, it is easy to see that also in this case the process shows some bottlenecks. Similarly to the previous simulation, one bottleneck is in correspondence with the opening of the request. The other bottleneck is in correspondence with the activity "request in-depth analysis" (182 instances waiting to execute it).

In this more realistic scenario, where activities actually have a likely duration, only about 10 instances reached the end of the process. All the others were in execution or stuck somewhere in the process when the 30 days of execution simulation ended.

2.6. Section final remarks

Professionals sometimes resist the idea of adopting pre-defined, well-designed processes in their work because they want the freedom to decide how to handle a situation. Moreover, they perceive such processes as slow to update to match the real, ever changing, world. This, however, happens also because of the lack of proper means for business process representation and management. Processes (often shared in oral form) are somewhat followed, in the end, but they remain underspecified and this creates problems not only to the management (both for what concerns supervision and for what concerns optimization or adaptation to changing conditions) but also to the professionals themselves because of misunderstandings and because of different interpretations.

This makes working remotely particularly costly and not so well accepted on both the sides of the management and of the workers.

We have practically shown to the involved company the advantages of a proper process representation and of the possibilities it opens to the managers for what concerns the analysis of what is going on (even when workers are not physically visible) as well as of what may go on, by simulating actual and possible scenarios.

Good process management does not aim at freezing a specific organization of the work, hampering evolution. On the contrary, it supports good evolution, that is, it supports identifying those deviations from the process, due to the expertise and the sensibility of the workers, that improve the performance. In turn, this step supports an easier integration in the company's processes of solutions that are developed bottom-up. We face this aspect in the following section.

3. Analysis of Real Process data

In this section, we describe how Process Mining Techniques [6] was used to analyze real data obtained from logging process executions. These data represent a precious source of information because they maintain how processes are carried out in reality, rather than as they are expected to be carried out. However, this information is particularly difficult to get because it does not plainly amount to the data but rather it is hidden inside the data.

Process Mining supports information mining from real data by exploiting a wide range of tools and techniques. We now report about the investigation carried out on the actual data that was extracted from the company databases, and that log all of the activities that were actually carried out in order to close actual tickets, which were opened by actual clients. Anonymity of the parts is mandatory here.

As an initial remark, we underline that the data analysis is still ongoing, so these results are partial because the outcomes are being discussed with the company representatives, and only after this phase will have ended we will have a complete assessment.

3.1. The Data

Shape of the data

The data supplied by the company consists of an Excel file containing three sheets:

- General information on the tickets.
- Detailed information on the state changes of the tickets.
- More detailed and heterogeneous information on the operations performed on the tickets.

The analysis that we performed considers the state in which a ticket is. A ticket state is expected to be Open, when the ticket is created (initial state), and to reach the state Closed at the end of the process (final state).

The analysis focused on 1) spotting anomalous handling of the tickets and 2) tips in improving the process by observing how workers did their jobs. Concerning the latter, it is, indeed, often the case that workers find shortcuts in performing some tasks, either because the system does not provide

some functionality they need, or because they have found a cheaper or more convenient way of performing it. Therefore, these situations represent a valuable source of information for companies.

Let us, now, describe the information that was given to us by the company.

Ticket States. The states in which a ticket can be are: Open, Assigned, In Progress (Troubleshooting in some previous version of process documentation), Customer Action, Partner Action, Solution Proposed, Resolved, Pending Approval, Obsolete (Superato), and Closed.

Ideally, a ticket should start in a state that is "Open" or "Assigned". When someone is working on the ticket it passes in the state "In progress". If more information is needed from the customer, then it goes to the state "Customer Action", while if some on field action is required to fix the problem (often outsourced to external partner), then the ticket moves to the state "Partner Action". Once a solution is found, then this is proposed to the customer and the ticket goes in the state "Solution Proposed". At this point, if the customer disagrees with the resolution of the ticket, then it goes again to "In progress". Otherwise, if the customer agrees or does not reply at all, the ticket goes in the state "Resolved" (in the latter case after 24 hours) and then it is manually or automatically "Closed" (after 72 hours by being in the "Resolved" state). If the ticket is closed because the problem does not exist anymore, it goes into the "Obsolete" state. Possible state transitions are summarized in Figure 8.

For each ticket state change, the dataset supplied by the company records two pieces of information: *Previous State and New State*.

Operation time. For each state change recorded in the dataset, the system also records the date and the time at which the change happens. This may support analysis of the overall duration of a ticket management process, although it does not record a start and an end timestamp for each state.

Priority. A priority is assigned to each ticket assigning a value on the scale: High, Medium, Low, and Very Low. The priority is a value that is automatically derived from two other pieces of information supplied by the customer, namely the *Urgency* and the *Impact as per ITIL best practice*. The former is meant to capture how important is for the customer that the problem is solved quickly; the latter captures how severe the problem is on the regular execution of the activities on the customer side. The priority value results from the urgency and impact indications applying a set of predefined rules. For instance, if both urgency and impact are "high" then the priority is "high" as well. A rule for each combination of values is defined.

Figure 8. Ticket state lifecycle

Request type. A ticket type is associated with a request from the customer. The company identified three different categories, ruled by agreements specified in the contracts signed with the customers. Rules for ticket management (such as, which requests can be handled as part of the contract and which require a new agreement) are out of the scope of our study. We are more interested in the processes in which each of the request types is handled within the company. Possible requests are:

- INC – Incident. This signals a problem as a consequence of which some tasks performed by the customer cannot be performed as wished.
- CR – Change Request. With this request, the customer is asking to change some functionality of the systems, to better support the execution of some tasks. These kinds of complex requests should be evaluated and authorized before they are implemented.
- SR – Service Request. This request is similar (in the way it is handled) to the Change Request case. It happens when the customer requires some small pre-authorized changes to the service (typically defined in a service catalog). Changes that can be implemented within the terms specified in the contract.

Category. Possible categories for the tickets are: Networking, Security, Collaboration, and Systems – Data Center. Through the Category, ticket managers can specify the technology area the request refers to. More details can be provided by filling also the Subcategory field (although from the data we can see that the subcategory is rarely specified).

Client. The information we have is anonymized. A code identifies the client the request refers to. The code ensures consistency and univocity: one code is associated with one and only one customer.

Applicant (Requester/Richiedente). Also this information is anonymized. A code is associated with the user opening the request.

Technician. For anonymity, also the technician taking care of the ticket is identified with a code. Although it is rare (according to the company) that a ticket passes to different technicians, the information stored in the dataset refers to the last one in the process, i.e. the one associated with the closure of the ticket.

Group. Process-wise, the data stored in the “Group” is quite informative. Specifically, it provides the category/skill level to which the technician belongs, distinguishing mainly between two categories: H1 and H2, where H1 identifies what is called “first-level” technicians, i.e. those who are expected to take care of a ticket in the first place, and are those having basics and general competences which are useful to solve part of the tickets and to hand-over the remaining ones to the right competent person. Indeed, with the code H2 the company identifies the “second-level” technicians, who are expected to have more in-depth and specific competencies to solve the problems.

If we consider the Excel sheet containing general information on the tickets, we can get further insights into the ticket management procedure.

Creation, Taking over, Resolution, Completion, and Due Date. Analyzing these dates in combination with the information described previously, may provide useful insights into real processes about ticket management in the company.

Hours spent. The semantics of this field is to store the amount of hours actually spent to solve the ticket (effort).

3.2. Data Statistics

The data contains records for 4202 tickets, and it was extracted by exporting only tickets in a final state given a fixed period of time. The alternative was to consider all state changes falling in a fixed period of time. However, this would have exported tickets in progress making it difficult to distinguish between anomalies and tickets in the phase of elaboration. Overall, we have 17848 records at our disposal for the analysis.

3.3. Analysis Methodology

This case study was used with the final aim of proposing a *methodology* to the company, that could be of support to their process analysis. The approach that we propose relies on techniques from *business process management* - in particular *process mining*, and *business intelligence*.

Thanks to the initial meetings with the domain experts from the company, we could understand the way in which the analysis of the processes and of the performances are usually carried on by the company. Two main reasons can trigger a targeted analysis: one is when some anomalous behavior is observed (like a ticket taking too long to be closed, or a complaint by a customer); another reason is when, by informal communications with workers, additional information on the implementation of processes is acquired. For instance, if an employee describes the use of the "In progress" state also when not foreseen by the procedure but because it simplifies the management of the tickets in some cases, then this is symptomatic of the need to adapt the procedure and the system to specific cases. These cases allow for the identification of process improvements.

In general, as we expected, the company was not familiar with process mining techniques and mainly relied on ad-hoc SQL queries over the database to extract quantitative and qualitative information. Process mining, instead, would support step-by-step analysis, also by way of a graphical representation and graphical reports that can be shown to the management.

So, as a first step, we showed to the company the potential of process mining tools and performed some basic analysis, such as showing the process map extracted from the data (see Figure 9). This helped to clarify the kind of analysis we referred to and to grasp the kind of data useful to perform it. After a few interactions with subsequent refinements of the provided data, we have converged on the dataset containing the information described above.

Several interactions were required for the team to understand the semantics of the data and the ideal process to be performed for ticket handling. These interactions were actually very useful to collect practices used by the workers, shortcomings of the systems, or shortcuts implemented by the workers. The responsible people we were having the meeting with could provide this information coming from informal interactions they had with the workers.

As a subsequent step, we asked the responsible person to identify some aspects of interest to be explored by querying the data, aiming at checking the conformance or divergence with the ideal process. Similarly, we listed several analyses that could be performed on the data. We discussed these possible analyses with the company and prioritized them according to the interest of the company in such analysis.

The last step consisted of identifying the most suitable technique to answer the identified queries, considering also a way of showing the results that could be intuitive and readable for the management of the company.

Figure 9. Process Map generated with DISCO by applying process discovery techniques

Summarizing, the performed steps are:

1. Gather the data;
2. Understand the semantics of the data;
3. Collect information on the actual execution of the processes and on informal communications;
4. Hypothesize queries of interest for the domain experts;
5. Suggest additional queries coming from the academic expertise;
6. Identify the best techniques to answer the queries and visualize the results.

3.4. The Analysis

In this section, we report the questions that guided our analysis and the results that we obtained. As said, at the time of writing the analysis is ongoing, so we present some initial results on which to start developing further analysis.

Analysis by clusters

During the interactions with the company, the interest in an analysis by clusters emerged. This analysis consists of partitioning the dataset into clusters, according to some parameters and performing the analysis for each cluster. Comparisons between each cluster process can also be made.

We started by considering two main dimensions:

1. *type* of request
 - INC for Incident,
 - SR for Service Request,
 - CR for Change Request;
2. *priority* associated with the ticket.

Let us start with the first dimension. We formulated the following question:

Question 1: Are there differences in how requests are handled based on the typology? How does the process of handling these cases differ and are there anomalies in how they are performed?

To answer this question we set a filter that we set to assume, in turn, one of the three possible values for the request types.

First, let us compare some values concerning the duration in the three cases.

	Num Variants	Num Traces	Median duration case	Mean duration case
INC	350	2427	6.9 d	17.2 d
SR	230	1573	7.6 d	22.3 d
CR	74	202	32.8 d	49 d

Some considerations emerge already comparing these values. In particular, it is not surprising that CR takes on average more time to be solved. In our view, indeed, handling these types of cases requires additional steps, that is first checking and agreeing on how to handle the request concerning the agreements in the contract. Then, it is reasonable to expect that implementing a change would require on average quite some time.

However, we also noticed how the service request and the incident type have comparable Median durations. In our view, this is a bit surprising since we would expect incident requests to be solved faster than a service request. This consideration could be supported or discarded by a domain expert only.

After considering the duration, let us have a look at the process executions. It is clear that for the clusters where fewer variants are present, the process maps appear less chaotic. For INC and SR it is quite difficult to look at the most detailed process map. Just to give an intuition we report the following map for INC type.

It is important to stress that since the company does not adopt an explicit and well-formed set of processes and the tool used to track activities does not enforce a ticket lifecycle (they are planning to adopt ticket lifecycle functionality in the future at least for some kind of ticket), it is impossible to compare the actual executions to the expected executions. Hence, the outcomes of the analysis can only be validated through the collaboration with the company experts, a step that is still to be done and that we expect will provide deep insight. The following part of the report highlights some odd behaviors that were detected by the analysis and that will be reported for a deeper investigation.

To this aim we, now, report and comment on three process maps (one for each type of request), that were produced by the process analysis tool gauging the parameters so that only the most frequent arcs are reported. Figures 10, 11 and 12 correspond to the INC, the SR, and the MR request types respectively.

Figure 10. Process Map for INC type

Figure 11. Process Map for SR type

Figure 12. Process Map for CR type

Figure 10, compared to Figures 11 and 12, shows that incident-type INC generally follows a more direct path from the opening to the closure of the ticket. For instance, we can see that only one direction (in this simplified view) is possible starting from the Open state, which refers to the direct assignment of the task to a technician. We suppose a technician of level 2 who will take care of solving the problem. If we look at the other two process maps, instead, we see more enable alternative forms of management.

Anyway, this is just the beginning. The analysis needed to be further refined because the outcome is still too complex (it is considering too many parameters). Accordingly, by looking at the possible states in which a ticket can be, we decided to focus on the state "Superato" (standing for "obsolete" in the semantics adopted by the company). This state is traversed by some of the process instances and, in our opinion, if it is traversed too few times, it may be symptomatic of a non-needed state. Therefore, we consider the three types of requests separately and consider only those variants traversing this state.

Question 2: For the three typologies of request, how is the "Superato" state used by the employees?

To answer this question we start by comparing the process map for the three request types.

For the INC process map, we observe that some instances pass from state "Superato" to state "Resolved" and then "Closed", while other instances pass from state "Superato" to state "Closed".

This highlights *how the semantics of "Resolved" is not clear*, at least for us it is not clear when a process instance can directly jump to the "Closed" state and when it has to pass through resolved.

A similar behavior occurs also for the request type SR. In this case, some other strange behaviors can also be observed. In particular, *there are instances that start in Open and then directly jump to the "Superato" state*. This may be plausible if a certain amount of time passes. We decided to investigate this aspect by looking at the minimum duration and we can see that there is an instance for which this transition happens in 31 seconds for the INC type. *This may be symptomatic of the use of "Superato" which differs from the expected one*. Additional background knowledge would be needed also in this case.

Figure 13. Process Map of minimum durations for the SR type

Minimum durations for the INC case seem to be more plausible. Indeed, from open to direct "Superato" at least 90 minutes pass. However, it is still a bit strange that from open to "assign" the minimum duration is 71 seconds, and from assigned to "Superato" 11.2 minutes only.

Figure 14. Process Map of minimum durations for the INC type

Another anomaly that should be clarified for the SR type with the company is that **from "In Progress" to "Superato" the minimum duration is 20 weeks**. This is a big difference compared to the duration from Open to "Superato". Actually, another strange behavior is that, as can be seen from Figure 13, for the SR case **there is one instance that from the state "Resolved" goes back to the state "Superato"**.

ACTION: We plan to deepen these analyses together with experts from the company in order to:

- 1) practically show them how such kind of analysis can be performed and what type of information one can get, and
- 2) to acquire additional domain knowledge to assess the anomalies of the processes that were identified with the help of the system.

Question 3: Is it true that cases that have higher priority are resolved faster?

This question disregards the process types and focuses on the priorities of the tickets.

We collected the following data.

	Num Variants	Num Cases	Median duration case	Mean duration case
High	8	10	15.1 d	35.1 d
Medium	505	4125	7.4 d	20.6 d
Low	9	9	9.9 d	22.3
Very Low	31	53	9	9

Two main observations arise. The first one concerns the number of variants and cases for each variant. Most of the cases and variants have priority "Medium" while all the other priorities have very few cases. This may be symptomatic of a bad use of the priorities (which also diminishes the value of considering the parameter). Data show that typically tickets get medium priority, as if priority were not used properly or was used a mean/default value (probably whenever the requester did not specify a value for Impact and Urgence).

Another observation concerns the duration. It comes as a bit surprising that requests with **high priority have median and mean duration which are higher than all other cases**. For instance, durations are even higher than durations for instances with the priority "Very Low". A possible justification could be provided by the level of difficulty for the high-priority cases, which could require more time to find a suitable solution. However, this is an open point that must be investigated further together with the company.

If we consider the process maps for the three cases (Figures 10-12), we can see that when priority is "high" the requests go from the state Open directly to the Assigned state. This, we believe, happens because, in order to accelerate the solution, the ticket is directly assigned to a technician. This sounds like **reasonable behavior**.

For the "medium" priority requests, only 603 cases over 4125 pass through the state Assigned directly from the Open state. The others traverse either the Partner Action, the Customer Action, or the In Progress states. However, **a strange behavior that needs to be clarified for priority "medium" is that there are cases that go from the Open to the Assigned states but, then, from Assigned they go back to the Open state and then go to the In Progress state (this could be related to standard ManageEngine SD behavior adopted in the initial period of use that was set to resend the ticket to Open state after every Customer interaction by incoming email or update through self service web portal)**.

3.5. Questions to be investigated next

The next steps for the process analysis consist in discussing with the company the analysis presented above. Indeed, to clarify what the justification for the behaviors highlighted above could be, there is the need for additional knowledge from the company reference person and, eventually, from the workers.

Besides this analysis direction, however, we identified a number of future directions the analysis could undertake. These will be discussed as well with the company in order to understand the level of interest the company may have in each of them.

To give some examples, we identified three main dimensions from which the analysis can be tackled: resources, process, and general.

From the resources point of view, interesting questions are:

- what is the organizational level involved in the process? In particular, is it possible to monitor the growth of competencies for the different roles involved in the process? Can we, for instance, observe cases where an employee was able to solve tasks with increasing levels of complexity?
- Does the ability to solve problems relate to the educational level and type of resources?
- In a conversation with the company, it emerged that technicians of level 1 were assigned more and more tasks to solve. What is the reason? Are they more skilled? are problems easier?
- Is there a mechanism for the company to collect workers' feedback and take them into account to improve the process?

From the point of view of processes, possible questions are:

- Once a ticket is assigned to a resource, is the resource handling the task till the end, or is delegated eventually to another resource? Is delegation ruled by some pattern?
- Is it the case that all instances in the state open or assigned eventually reach a closed or overcome state? Similarly, is the case that all instances in the state closed or overcome started from an open or assigned state?
- How many resources are employed in a single execution of the process?
- Tickets to be handled in the same way, are in reality following the same steps? Are there ticket types that are handled differently by different technicians?

Another interesting question could be:

- If we consider the overall process of ticket management, thus considering all types of tickets, how does the process look like? Are resources enough? Are there dependencies (e.g., due to limited resources) between different types of tickets, that emerge from this view?

4. Smart Working and Mountain Realities

Generalizing a bit the lessons learned after the reported activities we can say the following:

- Remote/hybrid models of work require tools that support collaboration. Many software systems allow forms of collaboration that can be performed even when the parties involved do not dwell in the same building and, rather, are geographically distributed. The ticketing system in the case study is but an example. More common tools are cloud systems, emails, chats. Allowing collaboration, however, does not mean to support collaboration because the realization of a (broadly speaking) “function” requires some kind of organization. Hence the possibility of designing, analyzing, sharing processes.
- The presence of a clear, well-designed process increases the trust of the parties in one another, and contributes to ensure the quality of the service.
- Even where the need of explicit processes/procedures is clear, without appropriate forms of representation it is tendentiously impossible to produce a complete model.
- The availability of a well-defined process must be complemented with the education of the workers in adopting the process and an integration of the process itself into the ICT infrastructure. Not understanding the reasons for following given procedures hinders their adoption. Collaborative tools, if not restrained or complemented with a view of the ongoing execution, and of the expected behavior, may be fertile ground for the creation of own approaches.
- The latter are neither good nor bad (innovation requires exploration) but innovation should not be confined to the individual, rather it should arise to the awareness of the company and, when appropriate, contribute to the improvement of the processes. Process analysis is crucial in this.
- Depending on the kind of service provided by the company, the cycle of process design, process analysis, and process improvement may require conspicuous efforts to the company. It cannot be fully outsourced or delegated because in order for processes to be effective, corporate culture is core.
- Many productive/service sectors that are present in mountain regions could benefit from the proposed tools/approaches. Among these, cheese and agricultural cooperatives/enterprises (e.g. for what concerns the organization of produce collection and transportation), tourism (e.g. alpine tours, ski lift maintenance), news and communication, healthcare (e.g. for what concerns the provision of assistance).

Last but not the least, processes must not necessarily capture the expected behavior inside a single company. It is, indeed, possible to design cross-organizational processes in order to account for many parties that cooperate. For instance, in the construction sector many specialized professionals/companies are involved in the realization of a project. Part of these collaborations are temporary and goal-oriented. Besides the completion of the ongoing analysis of the case study, a future direction of research may consist in investigating such higher level scenarios.

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